

Evaluation of Effectiveness of Early Clinical Exposure (ECE) in Clinical Physiology among Phase – 1 MBBS Students

Charu Kharbanda

Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, SIMSR, Kalol, Gandhinagar

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Charu Kharbanda

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Physiology lays the foundation of future clinical sciences. In the traditional system of medical education, it was mainly taught by means of didactic lectures, tutorials & practical classes. For comprehensive medical education goals, introducing new modalities is essential. Early clinical exposure (ECE) alongside traditional lectures can spark interest, enhance understanding & promote active learning.

Study type: Educational interventional study.

Place of study: SIMSR, Kalol, Gandhinagar.

Duration: 4 Months.

Participants: 150 students, Phase -1 MBBS (Academic batch 2023 – 2024).

Data collection tool: Pre – validated questionnaire in Google forms, Pre – validated perception questionnaire for students & faculty members. Five ECE topics were covered with the help of case-based scenarios, hospital visits & calling of specific patients with clinical signs to the classroom.

Results: MCQ marks with traditional teaching learning methods were $5.70 + 1.89$. Marks of students with ECE sessions were $7.18 + 1.89$. Students unpaired t – test was used to compare post test scores between exposure group & non-exposure group, which comes 6.433. P value was obtained as $P < 0.0001$.

Discussion: In my study significant difference found between scores obtained by exposure group & control group. Students trained by ECE were benefitted more when compared with students trained with traditional methods on learning modules of heart emergencies, Shock, Diabetes mellitus etc.

Conclusion: ECE can help in improved understanding of topic. ECE can be an effective technique in creating learning environment and help in achieving objectives.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Early Clinical Exposure, Teaching Learning Method.

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Introduction

Physiology lays the foundation of future clinical sciences. [1] In the traditional system of medical education, Clinical Physiology was mainly taught by means of didactic lectures, tutorials & practical classes. For comprehensive medical education goals, introducing new modalities is essential. Early clinical exposure (ECE) alongside traditional lectures can spark interest, enhance understanding & promote active learning. [2]

In the traditional teaching methods, students are engaged in the class rooms and laboratory practical during the first year of their education and clinical postings are introduced only in the second year.3 MCI in its Vision 2015 has insisted the need of clinical teaching exposure from first year onwards in all medical colleges of India through which the imaginary wall that always existed between the basic sciences and clinical sciences would have been broken and the application of basic knowledge in clinical correlation of patients would have been

achieved early & easily. [4] The Vision 2015 of Medical Council of India states that the Indian medical graduate (IMG) should have the necessary competencies (Knowledge, Skills and Attitude) to assume his or her role as a health care provider to the people of India and the world. [4] Also the goals of medical education should be learner-centred in which the student develops knowledge, skills and attitude respectively with cognitive, psychomotor and affective domains.5 Early Clinical Exposure (ECE) is one of the measures taken by MCI to enact its vision.

In Early Clinical exposure (ECE) the clinical training is started from first MBBS itself where clinical exposure is given together with the basic Physiology. [6,7] There are case based scenarios for class room discussions, hospital visits and calling of patients to class room for students' observation of clinical signs & symptoms under ECE.

Here the present study was planned to evaluate the effectiveness of ECE in Phase 1 MBBS students & to compare it with traditional methods such as didactic lectures.

Aim: To determine the effectiveness of Early Clinical Exposure (ECE) as Teaching Learning Method (TLM).

Objective

1. To evaluate the effectiveness of ECE in clinical Physiology teaching.
2. To analyse faculty members' & students' perception for Early clinical exposure (ECE).

Methodology

Study type: Educational interventional study.

Place of study: SIMSR, Kalol, Gandhinagar.

Duration: 4 months.

Participants: 150 students, Phase -1 MBBS (Academic batch 2023 – 2024)

Data collection tool:

- Pre – validated questionnaire in Google forms
- Pre – validated perception questionnaire for students & faculty members.

Five ECE topics were covered with the help of

case-based scenarios, hospital visits & calling of specific patients with clinical signs to the classroom. Five ECE topics were:

1. Heart Emergencies
2. Diabetes mellitus
3. ECG & its clinical correlation
4. Circulatory shock
5. Artificial kidney & Dialysis

Present analytic study was conducted on 150 first year students in the department of Physiology, SIMSR, Kalol, Gandhinagar. A separate orientation program was conducted for students (n=150) and faculty members (n=6) about the purpose of study & procedure.

Two groups were made Group A & Group B each having 75 students. In the first session, Group A was given ECE & group B was taught with traditional didactic lecture. Both groups were given questionnaire in Google form & results collected. In the next session Group B was given ECE while group A was taught with traditional method. Both groups were given questionnaire & result collected. Remaining sessions were done in the similar manner. In the end students' & faculty members' perception was taken on feedback form based on 5 – point Likert scale.

Figure 1:

Results: MCQ marks with traditional teaching learning methods were 5.70 + 1.89. Marks of students with ECE sessions were 7.18 + 1.89. Students unpaired t – test was used to compare post test scores between exposure group & non-exposure group which come 6.433. P value was obtained as P < 0.0001.

Table 1: Effectiveness of ECE as TLM

MCQ marks	Traditional TLM	ECE	t – value	P value
	5.70 + 1.89	7.18 + 1.89	6.433	<0.0001

Values are expressed as Mean ± SD. SD = Standard deviation.

Perception of students regarding ECE

Figure 2: Perception of students regarding ECE

Discussion

Early clinical exposure (ECE) involves an active learning from patients by practicing clinicians as early as first year of MBBS.8 Now a days ECE program is included in undergraduate medical curriculum. [8,9]

National medical council (NMC) of India has stressed the need of ECE in first year MBBS students. Objective behind this is to familiarize the medical students with patients earlier so that students can sharpen their clinical skills & communication skills as well. [10,11]

In my study significant difference found between

scores obtained by exposure group & control group. Students trained by ECE were benefitted more when compared with students trained with traditional methods on learning modules of heart emergencies, Shock, Diabetes mellitus etc.

These results were similar with study by Motilal et al (2014) in which the students exposed to ECE scored better marks compared with traditional TLM. [12] This study also found similar results as study conducted by Dinesh et al (2019) where they found significant difference in scores of exposure & non-exposure groups. The students trained by ECE scored more than control group on learning modules of anaemia & jaundice. [13]

Perception of teachers' regarding ECE

Figure 3: Perception of teacher's regarding ECE

Similar results were found in the study conducted by Lonke Boken et al (2009). They found that participants considered real patient encounters more instructive and more authentic than simulated patients & normal subjects. [14] A study by Solomon et al (2007) which studied the attitude of medical students towards ECE in learning endocrine Physiology on 56 medical students.

They reported that ECE increased their interest for the subject & motivated them to read more. Students also felt that ECE enhanced their understanding of endocrine Physiology, enabled them to remember the subject better & also helped them to integrate their knowledge.

Many students also said that ECE increased their sensitivity towards patients' problems and needs. [8]

Students' perception regarding ECE

27% students strongly agreed & 54% agreed that ECE increased teacher student communication. 24% strongly agreed & 55% agreed that ECE with patients increased their active participation. 39% strongly agreed & 49% agreed that ECE helped in better understanding of key concepts. 39% strongly agreed & 52% agreed that there is more implication of knowledge with ECE. 62% agreed that there is

need of more sessions of ECE. Lastly, 57% students found ECE more engaging than traditional teaching learning methods.

Teachers' perception regarding ECE

61% of teachers strongly agreed & 28% agreed that with ECE there is increase in teacher students' communication. 44% strongly agreed & 44% agreed that with ECE there is conceptual learning. 50% strongly agreed & 39% agreed that understanding of key concept is better with ECE. 50% strongly agreed & 39% agreed that there should be vertical integration with clinical subjects. 40% strongly agreed & another 40% agreed that they felt motivated & more empowered after taking ECE sessions. 33% strongly agreed & 50% agreed that they found ECE sessions more engaging.

Conclusion

ECE improved the learning environment & also promoted active learning as reflected in the test score. The introduction of the innovative curriculum with ECE coincided with improved academic performance.

The students opined that this innovative method to learn clinical Physiology trained them in clinical skills & improved their attitude towards the newer trends in medical education. The students &

teachers perceived the ECE method to be valuable learning tool in clinical Physiology which improved their reasoning skills & motivated them to learn.

ECE can help in improved understanding of topic. ECE can be an effective technique in creating learning environment and help in achieving objectives.

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